

Eastern England SDE SATRE Self-Assessment: Findings, Insights and Iterations

Tom Billins, Adebambo Ayileka, Laura Clarke, Onesimus Ekechi,
Adam Loveday, Alexis Joannides, Keiran Raine

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Eastern England SDE SATRE Self-Assessment: Findings, Insights and Iterations

VISTA SATRE Workstream Final Report

Authors

Tom Billins (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0009-0002-8601-2004)

Adebambo Ayileka (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0009-0003-8196-4265)

Laura Clarke (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0000-0002-5989-6898)

Onesimus Ekechi (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0009-0005-9040-0167)

Adam Loveday (Eastern England Secure Data Environment & Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, ORCID: 0000-0002-5440-4305)

Alexis Joannides (Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, University of Cambridge, ORCID: 0000-0002-6618-256X)

Keiran Raine (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0000-0002-5634-1539)

1. Executive summary

This report presents the outcomes and reflections from VISTA Work Package 1, the SATRE (Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments) (Version 1.0) (Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE), 2023)¹ self-assessment conducted by the Eastern England Secure Data Environment (EE-SDE)² team, comprising colleagues from Health Innovation East (HIE) and Cambridge University Hospitals (CUH). The assessment formally evaluated the SDE's conformity against SATRE, using a structured, collaborative, panel-based methodology that drew on best practice from NHS SDE accreditation and ISO (International Organisation for Standardisation) aligned controls.

Key findings demonstrate that the EE-SDE is built on a robust and compliant foundation, having full conformity across all mandatory SATRE statements and high scores in recommended and optional areas. Where gaps were identified, these related to enhancements rather than deficiencies, and targeted improvement actions have already been initiated. The assessment process delivered several benefits:

- Strengthened governance and technical controls, with evidence interpreted consistently across disciplines
 - Immediate operational improvements, including new reporting dashboards, training needs analysis, and enhanced quality-management data capture
 - Accelerated development of advanced capabilities, such as regular configuration validation, high-performance computing, and improvement to disclosure control processes
- Enhanced collaboration within the team and with national partners, supported by active participation in Data and Analytics Research Environments (DARE) UK working groups and the SATRE Short Life Working Group (SLWG)³

There were also challenges encountered:

- The need to balance flexibility and maintainability in user environments
- Addressing terminology differences between SATRE and other frameworks
- Framing cost-recovery models transparently

Findings from this analysis have shaped the direction of our continual improvement process. As the EE-SDE had been built to align with draft versions of SATRE, it was expected to perform well, and this exercise provided a structured check against the published SATRE v1.0 specification. The assessment highlighted where further maturity is needed, in many cases in areas where user demand has been low or where scale of use has not yet justified additional investment during early platform delivery. Overall, the SATRE framework helped sharpen our focus for future assurance needs. The EE-SDE is set up to deliver a secure research environment aligned with national expectations; addressing the findings will primarily improve our ability to operate at scale.

2. VISTA project background

VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025 Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TRevolution standards and AI capabilities within the EE-SDE.

The aims of VISTA were to support and enhance existing EE-SDE processes. Demonstrating how large-scale AI-enabled research can be conducted safely, efficiently and consistently, whilst helping other TREs adopt these approaches. There were four specific aims:

- To complete a structured self-assessment against the SATRE benchmark specification and develop actionable recommendations to inform the next phase of TRE development
- Test and refine semi-automated research output checking in the EE-SDE
- Safely train and export ML and AI models from the TRE
- Support readiness for AI models to be deployed in NHS services

VISTA adopted three TRevolution capabilities: SATRE aligns the EE-SDE with a community driven specification adopted across UK TREs and now evolving to include federation and ML output control capabilities. SACRO⁴ enables more efficient and auditable disclosure checking by applying SDC principles directly within analytical workflows. SACRO-ML⁵ extends this to ML models through ante-hoc and post-hoc risk assessments, including SafeModel evaluation and membership inference attack testing.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) was embedded through existing EE-SDE structures, including the Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG). This ensured that development of SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML reflected public expectations around transparency, accountability and appropriate use of automation.

This work package report focuses on insights from the Eastern England SDE self-assessment of implementation conformity and alignment with the SATRE specification.

3. Methodology and approach

The SATRE self-assessment was carried out as a structured and collaborative exercise involving colleagues across Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust (CUH) who work on the Eastern England SDE (EE-SDE) programme.

The platforms team at Health Innovation East led on the technical domains, while Information Governance (IG) and wider governance colleagues across Health Innovation East and CUH contributed to the IG, data protection, and organisational controls. Each domain had a designated lead for their respective area (IG, Computing Technology and Information Security, Data Management, and Supporting Capabilities). Leads were responsible for drafting the initial evidence statements and provisional scores, with other team members reviewing, challenging, and refining the responses. This panel-based review helped maintain consistency and avoid individual interpretation bias, reflecting our approach to similar assessments such as the NHS England SDE accreditation⁶ This approach helped ensure evidence was interpreted consistently for both internal improvement and any future external assurance. Equally, by using this method, we laid a clear foundation for the subsequent assessment outcomes and lessons learnt.

The assessment drew on a mixture of tools and reference frameworks. We mapped our evidence to SATRE's published clauses and used an internal scoring process to test the type of criteria expected to be formalised within the DARE UK programme. Prior experience with external assurance frameworks (including SDE accreditation and ISO-aligned controls) supported the interpretation of requirements and the articulation of evidence.

Evidence was gathered through focused workshops, cross-team discussions, and structured document reviews. Workshops were used to validate understanding across organisations, surface gaps, and agree on draft scores. Document reviews allowed us to test whether policies, procedures, and operational records met the SATRE requirements and supported our narrative. Where uncertainties emerged, we followed up with subject-matter experts to ensure accuracy and completeness.

This systematic methodology aligns with our bid's commitment to "formally assess our SDE's implementation conformity against SATRE" and provided an opportunity to trial the scoring approach likely

to be adopted under the DARE UK programme. By grounding the assessment in structured evidence, cross-team validation, and a consistent scoring process, we ensured the exercise was more than a descriptive review and instead a robust evaluation of readiness and maturity.

4. Roles and contributions

The Eastern England SDE was built and is operated by a multi-disciplinary team which draws expertise from software engineering, cloud security, data management, IG, and programme coordination. The assessment and review of the SATRE clauses were shared out across the team as described in Table 1.

Role	Computing Technology and Information Security	Data Management	Information Governance	Supporting Capabilities
Cloud Security Engineer				
Platform Technical Lead				
IG, Ethics, and Legal, Workstream Manager				
IG, Ethics, and Legal, Workstream Lead				
Commercial Workstream Manager				
Data Manager				
Programme Delivery Manager				

Table 1: The different sections of the SATRE assessment were completed by different members of the team.

4.1 Why the distribution matters

Mapping responsibilities to SATRE domains ensured that technical controls (e.g., Infrastructure as Code (IaC), cloud security policies) and governance artefacts (e.g., IG procedures and onboarding guidance) were evidenced by the teams that operate them. This reduced corrective work, improved clause-level accuracy, and shortened the time to consensus during the scoring panels.

4.2 Link to the assessment outcome

This structure directly underpinned the domain-level scores reported in the assessment outcome, with each lead accountable for evidence completeness and clause interpretation.

5. Assessment outcome

The self-assessment⁷ shows that the EE-SDE has been built on a strong and compliant foundation, with full conformity across all mandatory SATRE requirements. This confirms that the platform meets the core expectations for security, governance and data management needed for safe handling of sensitive health data.

The EE-SDE performed strongly. Overall performance across both recommended and optional criteria was high:

- **Data Management and Information Governance – 100%**
Achieved full compliance across all categories, demonstrating clear, established controls aligned with national standards
- **Computing Technology and Information Security – 97%**
No gaps in mandatory controls; areas for improvement relate to recommended clauses, equating to potential enhancements rather than substantive deficiencies
- **Supporting Capabilities – 94%**
No gaps in mandatory controls; areas for improvement were in recommended clauses where documentation and user-facing processes could be further strengthened

The headline results can be found in Table 2. The full SATRE self-assessment results (including statement-level scores, evidence statements, and identified improvements) are published on the SATRE UK TRE website⁵.

The **overall score of 98%** indicates a high level of maturity and close alignment with the SATRE specification. The small number of improvement areas identified will form part of a targeted enhancement plan, indicated later, to support readiness for future DARE UK-aligned scoring and assurance processes.

Domain	# of statements	Mandatory	Recommended	Optional	Overall
Computing technology and Information Security	58	100%	93%	100%	97%
Data management	34	100%	100%	100%	100%
Information governance	37	100%	100%	100%	100%
Supporting Capabilities	18	100%	91%	N/A	94%
Overall score	147	100%	95%	100%	98%

Table 2: Overall percentage scores for the four SATRE domains across the three different statement types, mandatory, recommended, and optional

These results confirm that our foundational controls are robust. Areas with reduced scores are already being addressed through continuous improvement, rather than indicating any fundamental weaknesses or need for urgent remediation.

6. SATRE impact

The SDE was designed and implemented alongside the draft versions of the SATRE specification, although core architectural and governance decisions were primarily driven by NHS requirements and organisational assurance frameworks such as the NHS Data Security Protection Toolkit (DSPT)⁸. The approach also benefited from input from experienced governance professionals, researchers and patient engagement programmes to inform system design. As a specification for those with limited access to expertise or ability to run engagement sessions, the framework provides a solid foundation. The technical implementation and supporting functions provide greater insight for research than data security focused frameworks such as DSPT or ISO/IEC 27001:2022⁹ can provide.

The EE-SDE has been developed with constant consideration of researcher input and project feasibility requirements. This avoids building features with limited short-term utility or over-specifying the system with little demand. This has impacted decisions on optional or recommended clauses of the SATRE specification and in some cases the maturity of mandatory elements. Similarly, attention is paid to clauses in the context of the wider Five Safes framework (Ritchie, 2017)¹⁰.

Here we identify some areas that introduced challenges due to variability of expectations and perceptions.

Clause 2.1.2 (recommended) “an environment familiar to users” was challenging for the EE-SDE due to the wide background of potential users. Those from a pure research background are more flexible than those from NHS analytics disciplines. A pragmatic decision was made to primarily provide a Linux (Ubuntu) desktop environment to balance cost, usability and future extensibility. A limited Windows implementation is available for specific application needs.

2.1.3 (optional) “Eyes-off analysis” was not considered suitable for the level of maturity of the project. In addition to challenges in data description and modelling, this would not remove the need for evaluation of analysis results prior to egress. Additionally, this had the potential to increase administrative and technical burden in the short term. This may be considered in future once pipelines and data models have matured.

2.1.7 (optional) Some elements of “shared project resources” were designed into the core platform but are limited to the Linux environment and file systems. Data requirements for known projects were evaluated to ensure build, maintenance and costs were appropriate for platform maturity. Other shared resources are being developed in line with user feedback.

2.2.5 (mandatory) We felt “a development environment that mirrors your production environment” was insufficient when considering permissions policies in the cloud. An area with reduced control is necessary to prototype ideas. A 4-stage environment is used:

1. Development – allowing for manual or locally executed IaC pipelines to facilitate rapid research and development (R&D)
2. Test – Deployments via automation roles, relaxed ability to view configuration and logging, integration of all pipelines
3. Stage – Permissions reflecting the production environment

4. Production – The only area with live data

When it comes to project costs the EE-SDE found some elements of the specification more challenging to frame a response when working under a cost-recovery model.

2.3.1, 4.4.1, 4.4.2 (mandatory, mandatory, recommended) - Fixed costs relating to project setup and onboarding are highlighted at the outset of an application along with a projection of anticipated compute and storage costs based on research requirements. However, compute and storage costs are incurred based on actual usage, not flat fees. This enables flexibility, the ability to test concepts on small hardware and then scale to a larger instance. This also aligns with NHS and SDE environmental expectations by avoiding running compute when not in use. Available compute instances are controlled by project specification, but users can start, stop and rescale compute as needed within these bounds via the portal. Projects have budgets associated which periodically notify the lead user of consumption, alongside a weekly review of project budgets by the platform administrators.

These interpretations, agreed in panel review, clarified clause intent for our context and directly generated the targeted improvement actions captured in Lessons Learnt and implemented in Evidence of Impact.

7. Lessons learnt

The SATRE assessment process provided assurance that the EE-SDE is underpinned by strong governance, and technical controls, as well as a proportionate researcher-focused design. Collaboration across Health Innovation East and CUH worked well, and a multi-disciplinary approach ensured evidence could be interpreted consistently even where SATRE clauses were open to interpretation. Engagement with DARE UK peers was also beneficial in helping benchmark assumptions and confirm that areas of uncertainty were shared across the wider community.

The exercise highlighted several challenges. Some SATRE clauses did not align neatly with terminology or expectations used in ISO/IEC 27001:2022, DSPT, or the NHS SDE accreditation, and this occasionally led to ambiguity when determining the correct score or drafting the narrative. The variation in expectations across different user groups, particularly in relation to clause 2.1.2 on “an environment familiar to users”, required careful balancing between flexibility, maintainability, and future extensibility. Optional and recommended clauses relating to advanced capabilities (such as eyes-off analysis or shared project resources) also illustrated that SATRE can sometimes assume a level of maturity that is difficult to reach early during a platform’s lifecycle.

SATRE nonetheless provides more specificity than ISO/IEC 27001:2022 and DSPT, particularly in areas unique to secure research environments such as analytical tooling, researcher workflows, disclosure control, and project lifecycle management. This granularity made SATRE a more actionable framework for identifying practical capability gaps and highlighted areas for enhancement now included in the improvement roadmap. For example, we have implemented organisational projects which allow private assets for a group to be approved once and linked to multiple research projects since the formal assessment to reduce both end user and operational burden. This is currently entering an evaluation stage.

The assessment also showed that while technical and governance evidence is strong, some internal documentation would benefit from earlier consolidation. In several places the underlying controls were

mature, but the supporting artefacts (training materials, onboarding guidance, user-facing process descriptions) were not yet packaged in a SATRE-ready format and required additional work during the workshops. Finally, framing responses to the cost-related clauses underscored the tension between SATRE's expectations and the financial reality of operating a cloud-based platform under a cost-recovery model.

Several improvements would streamline future assessments. The cross-mapped control set¹¹ that aligns SATRE, ISO/IEC 27001:2022, and NHS SDE standards that has been developed will reduce duplication, support consistent interpretation, and make it easier to evidence compliance across frameworks going forward, further development of this control set is welcomed. Establishing a short SATRE induction pack for contributors would help build a shared understanding of scoring logic and provide clause definitions from the outset. Earlier preparation of operational artefacts and user-facing documentation would also reduce the effort required during the assessment window. Maintaining a centralised evidence library aligned to SATRE domains will help ensure updates are captured continuously rather than retrospectively.

Overall, the process demonstrated that the EE-SDE's foundational controls are robust, and that SATRE can be used effectively to structure and prioritise maturity improvements (Table 3). The lessons from this cycle will support a more efficient, better aligned, and more predictable approach should SATRE scoring become formalised.

Area	EE-SDE	SATRE
What worked well	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Panel scoring & cross-mapping (ISO 27001/DSPT/NHS SDE) reduced ambiguity Workshops built shared understanding Multi-disciplinary review enabled consistent interpretation of evidence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detailed SATRE clauses enabled more actionable gap identification Framework supported focused discussion of secure research environment capabilities
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controls were mature in practice; supporting artefacts needed consolidation into a SATRE-ready evidence pack Evidence collation was effective, and would be more efficient with earlier consolidation of artefacts Deliberate balancing of user flexibility with maintainability and operational resilience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terminology and assumptions misaligned with ISO/DSPT/NHS SDE Some clauses assume higher platform maturity Cost recovery expectations difficult to apply to cloud models
Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scoring supported prioritisation for the next phase of maturity and scale Accelerated improvements to operational reporting Training needs analysis, and assurance evidence Stronger Health Innovation East-CUH collaboration Reusable templates and control mappings developed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SATRE operated effectively as a maturity shaping framework Greater relevance than ISO/DSPT for research workflows; analytical tooling, disclosure control, and project lifecycle management.
Forward look	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bring evidence collation forward (maintain 'assessment-ready' artefacts between cycles) Maintain a central SATRE-aligned evidence library to reduce repeat collation Continue evaluating operational outcomes alongside compliance Extend cross-mapped control set to further reduce duplication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide concise SATRE induction materials Clarify expectations for cost recovery clauses Refine assumptions around platform maturity and cloud native operation

Table 3: A summary of EE-SDE and SATRE perspectives on what worked well, challenges, benefits and the forward look from the SATRE self-assessment

8. Evidence of impact

The SATRE assessment directly informed a series of tangible improvements to the EE-SDE’s operational and governance framework. Scoring across recommended and optional areas, such as documentation collation and user-facing process clarity, helped prioritise targeted enhancements. As a result, our plan was refined to focus on the following:

- Amazon Web Services (AWS) reporting dashboards which aggregate security and configuration findings across the platform to support issue tracking, remediation planning, and ongoing operational assurance, (Figures 1, 2, and 3) were introduced to improve oversight and transparency

Figure 1. AWS Security Hub CSPM. Findings by Region Dashboard

Figure 2. AWS GuardDuty Dashboard

Figure 3. AWS Inspector Dashboard

- A structured training needs analysis identified role-specific skills gaps, which are being addressed through tailored training plans embedded in new-starter onboarding, including mandatory statistical disclosure control training for data management roles

Enhanced quality-management data capture was implemented through generation of data mapping reports for data prepared under a FITFILE solution and internally developed Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) pipelines, enabling transparent interrogation of data transformations by research teams and auditors as well as supporting audit requirements. These initiatives were launched during the assessment due to the clear benefit. They now form part of the SDE's operational flow.

The assessment helped confirm existing advanced capabilities, highlight areas requiring further maturity, and shape the ongoing roadmap.

Prioritised workstreams included:

- Configuration validation (in place prior to the assessment), which the SATRE process evidenced as a mature control, providing consistent verification of deployed configuration, however some areas could be developed further to validate on a schedule
- High-performance computing architecture identified through the SATRE assessment as a conditional future capability. To be assessed based on demonstrable research demand and viable funding models for projects
- Improved statistical disclosure controls, to enhance data privacy and compliance
- Long-term archiving in standard formats (in place prior to the assessment and confirmed through the SATRE process), supporting sustainability, data reuse, and future assurance
- Streamline metadata cataloguing (identified through the SATRE assessment and currently in progress), to improve discoverability and management of data assets
- Strengthen user-facing documentation (as part of continuous improvement), to support clearer navigation and understanding of platform workflows

We will continue to align training and onboarding with emerging NHS SDE requirements, recognising that related guidance from DARE UK may inform future standards. These outcomes represent concrete enhancements to both technical capability and assurance processes. The exercise clarified where the EE-SDE's controls were already mature and where targeted development would further strengthen resilience, usability, or scalability. Lessons learnt are now informing the next iteration of the SDE architecture and its alignment with the national Health Data Research Service (HDRS)¹², ensuring that future versions of the platform continue to meet evolving SATRE expectations.

Overall, the assessment led to the creation or refinement of several controls, sharpened the EE-SDE's improvement priorities, and strengthened readiness for future national assurance frameworks. The SATRE framework itself provided a uniquely detailed lens for assessing an SDE, enabling more precise identification of how standards are achieved and where further progress is needed.

9. Collaboration and engagement

The DARE UK bid emphasised active participation in DARE UK communities and working groups. The EE-SDE team contributed to the SATRE Short Life Working Group (SLWG), which was headed by Jenny Johnston. Regular engagement took place through the SATRE Weekly meetings, attended by team members, alongside colleagues from Dundee, University College London (UCL), and other partner organisations.

9.1 Group contributions:

- The team contributed to discussions on SATRE clause interpretation, evidence requirements, and operationalising compliance in diverse research environments
- A team member was actively involved in the SLWG's mapping of SATRE controls against other assurance frameworks. This collaborative work clarified where SATRE aligns with existing standards and where it introduces unique requirements for TREs
- The group's mapping analysis identified 22 controls unique to SATRE, highlighting its added value in areas such as project-specific costing, dev/test environments, and operational maturity
- As a key output, the SLWG published the SATRE control mapping and related disclosure on Zenodo seeking feedback from the wider TRE community and supporting broader discussion and engagement

9.2 Feedback and shared learnings:

- The mapping work received feedback from peers across the TRE community, which was used to refine the mapping and inform presentations at national events, including the TRE Community Conference in Leeds
- The collaborative process highlighted the importance of transparency, public trust, and operational maturity in TREs, and demonstrated how SATRE builds on and extends established best practice
- Shared learnings from other regions and TREs were incorporated, ensuring outputs reflected a broad range of operational contexts and challenges

Alongside professional collaboration through DARE UK working groups, we also prioritised public-facing engagement by translating our SATRE activity into accessible web content for researchers, partners and the wider public. This ensured the rationale for aligning to SATRE, and the practical implications for how the EE-SDE is governed and operated, were communicated in plain language rather than remaining solely within technical assurance documentation. An excerpt from the current iteration of this website content is provided in Appendix 14.1, with an earlier iteration included in Appendix 14.2, showing how our public narrative has been refined over time as the programme and our evidence base matured.

This engagement has strengthened the EE-SDE's alignment with national expectations and ensured that local implementation benefits from the collective experience of the DARE UK community. The publication of the SLWG's outputs on Zenodo provides a lasting resource for the TRE community and demonstrates the value of collaborative, cross-sector working.

10. Conclusion

This report has reflected on the EE-SDE's SATRE self-assessment, documenting not only the processes and outcomes, but also the reasoning behind our approach and the value realised through this exercise. By adopting a panel-based, cross-disciplinary methodology, we ensured that evidence was robust, consistent, and defensible, drawing on best practice from NHS SDE accreditation and ISO-aligned controls.

The assessment demonstrated strong conformity with SATRE requirements, with high scores across all domains and targeted actions identified for areas requiring further enhancement. Operational improvements, such as the introduction of reporting dashboards, structured training analysis, and enhanced quality-management, were implemented as a direct response to the assessment findings. The process also accelerated the development of advanced technical capabilities and strengthened our assurance framework.

Collaboration and engagement with the wider DARE UK community, particularly through the SATRE SLWG led by Jenny Johnston, provided valuable opportunities to share lessons, and contribute to national outputs, including published group papers on Zenodo. Feedback and shared learning from these groups have informed our continuous improvement and ensured our work remains aligned with national standards and expectations.

Looking ahead, the lessons learnt from this cycle will guide future assessments and platform development. Priorities include earlier preparation of operational artefacts, standardised induction for contributors, maintenance of a centralised evidence library, and ongoing evaluation of both compliance and operational value. The SATRE framework has proven to be a powerful tool for shaping maturity, driving collaboration, and supporting readiness for future assurance requirements.

By embedding these insights and actions, the EE-SDE is well positioned to continue delivering a secure, effective, and nationally aligned research environment.

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The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

12. Glossary

Five Safes – A widely used framework for designing and assessing safe access to sensitive data across five dimensions: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data and Safe Outputs (considered together to achieve “safe use”)

AWS – Amazon Web Services

CUH – Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust

CUHP – Cambridge University Health Partners, academic health science centre with a mission to improve patient care by uniting the NHS, Industry and Academia

DARE UK – Data and Analytics Research Environments UK, is a programme aimed towards establishing a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments.

EE-SDE – Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

ETL – Extract, Transform and Load process involves extracting data from various sources, transforming it into a suitable format, and loading it into a data warehouse.

FITFILE – The FITFILE technology platform delivers safe, scalable at source data record processing and multi-source linkage.

HDRS – UK Health Data Research Service (HDRS), backed by a £600m investment from the government and Wellcome.

HIE – Health Innovation East, the innovation arm of the NHS in the East of England.

IaC – Infrastructure as Code, practice of managing and provisioning IT infrastructure through machine-readable configuration files

ISO/IEC 27001:2022 – The international standard that sets requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and continually improving an Information Security Management System (ISMS) to manage information security risks.

NHS DSPT – NHS Data Protection and Security Toolkit is an online self-assessment tool for health and care organisations to measure performance against the National Data Guardian’s 10 data security standards and GDPR requirements

SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and Machine Learning, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained Machine Learning models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SATRE SLWG – SATRE Short Life Working Group led by Jenny Johnston

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

TREvolution – A DARE UK programme developing and testing standards and reference implementations to support more consistent, interoperable Trusted Research Environments (TREs), including components such as SATRE (architecture/specification) and related tooling

UCL – University College London

UKRI - UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT).

VISTA – Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI, is the project package aimed towards delivering tools to enhance Statistical Disclosure Checking, support in TREs for Machine Learning, and also for establishing a benchmarking standard for Trusted Research Environments.

Zenodo - is a multi-disciplinary open research repository hosted by CERN and commissioned by the European Commission through the OpenAIRE project to support the Open Data and Open Access movements in Europe. Data, software and all research related digital artifacts up to 50 GB in all formats and from any stage of the research lifecycle can be submitted. All uploads are assigned with a digital object identifier (DOI) to make them citeable.

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14. Appendices

14.1. Public-facing summary of SATRE evaluation ([EE-SDE website extract](#))

Secure by design

The Secure Data Environment platform is designed to securely hold data and prevent misuse, without affecting researchers' ability to use data for vital research.

It is regularly and independently tested against security vulnerabilities, achieving the internationally recognised ISO 27001 accreditation. It has also been internally assessed against the SATRE Framework, scoring 100% against all mandatory components.

The technology of the environment prevents any directly identifying information from entry to the space where researchers can access it. Each approved research project receives its own private secure space, and data cannot be moved between research spaces.

The environment prevents researchers from copying, altering or deleting raw data and from combining it with any other data source beyond those which they have approval to use.

The environment also controls what information can leave the environment. When researchers have completed their analysis, the research outputs (results) must first be verified to ensure no individual patient information can be released. Verification is done by trained professionals and can be supported through assistive technology.

[Read our SATRE evaluation report here >](#)

14.2. Public-facing summary of SATRE evaluation (previous iteration of EE-SDE website extract)

How we keep data safe

Our SATRE Evaluation

What is SATRE?

SATRE (Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments) is a national framework developed through the DARE UK programme. It helps Secure Data Environments (SDEs) measure their maturity and compliance with best practice standards for security, governance, and data management. SATRE promotes transparency, consistency, and trust in how health data is accessed for research. Learn more on the [DARE UK website](#).

Why did we take part?

The East of England SDE participated in the SATRE self-assessment as part of the VISTA programme. This national initiative supports secure, ethical, and efficient data access for research. Our evaluation helps demonstrate compliance with national standards and identify areas for continuous improvement. These standards build on our existing commitments to safeguarding data through robust privacy, security and integrity measures, detailed [here](#).

Headline Results

Our SATRE scores show strong performance across all mandatory requirements, confirming that the East of England SDE meets essential standards for security, governance, and operational resilience.

Domain	Total number of clauses	Mandatory	Recommended	Optional	Overall
Computing technology and Information Security	58	100%	93%	100%	97%
Data management	34	100%	100%	100%	100%
Information governance	37	100%	100%	100%	100%
Supporting Capabilities	18	100%	91%	N/A	94%
Grand Total	147	100%	95%	100%	98%

For full details, visit our SATRE evaluation on the [official site](#) and our [downloadable PDF report here](#).

What does this mean for the SDE?

The East of England Secure Data Environment demonstrates strong compliance with national standards for security and governance, making it a reliable platform for health data research. High scores in mandatory areas confirm robust foundations, while recommended and optional areas highlight opportunities for enhancement in usability and advanced features.

What's next?

We will continue improving by:

- Making it easier to set up systems and automatically keep track of important details about the data.
- Improving staff training, adding simple dashboards to show progress, and upgrading tools to check quality.
- Adding powerful new features like faster computing and stronger protections to keep sensitive information secure.

These steps will strengthen resilience, usability, and innovation, ensuring the East of England SDE remains a leading example of best practice.